

WORK MOTIVATION ON SERVICE DELIVERY OF NON-TEACHING PERSONNEL

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ABSTRACT

The extent of the manifestation of service delivery provided by the non-teaching personnel in the Department of Education is aligned to the Quality Policy in terms of quality, timeliness, and accuracy which is associated with the level of their work motivation. The descriptive correlational approach using a questionnaire was utilized to analyze the data. Findings synthesized show that teacher-respondents were highly satisfied that the non-teaching personnel is doing their job very well with the quality, timeliness, and accuracy of service that they can provide. However, it differed from what non-teaching personnel felt of themselves in serving their customers, where they believed that it has enough level of quality, timeliness, and accuracy. Moreover, in terms of the level of work motivation, it was evident that non-teaching personnel are highly motivated on their job as perceived by themselves. On the other hand, their level of work motivation has no significant relationship with service delivery. Responses from the teachers on service delivery were not the indicators that set their level of work motivation. No matter how high the responses of the teaching respondents towards their services, it does not compel non-teaching personnel to become more motivated in doing their job which implies other factors set their work motivation. Prioritizing the delivery of services, this study aimed to propose a service delivery plan designed for the non-teaching personnel which will serve as the foundation for deciding what training is required or should be developed to assist them and the organization in achieving the goals and objectives. Assisting them in aligning their requirements will improve the likelihood of greater possibilities for development. A successful service delivery plan that emphasizes passion for growth will result in a culture of innovation that contributes significantly to the delivery of high-quality services.

Keywords: Department of Education, work motivation, service delivery, non-teaching personnel, Philippines